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Mapping Complex Technologies via Science-Technology Linkages; The Case of Neuroscience

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Introduction

Times of accelerating technological change (Butler, 2016), growing interdisciplinarity of science and technology (Porter and Rafols, 2009) as well as increasing complexity of science and technology systems (Catalán et al., 2020) call for fast and responsive techniques to quantify, map, and understand technology development. Doing so is paramount to assess, influence, and facilitate the development of complex and interdisciplinary emerging technologies with potentially high economic and social impact, such as neuroscience, genetics, and artificial intelligence.

A large share of technology development builds on advances in science, where existing studies have demonstrated the rising interactions between science and technology and the important role science has played in accelerating technologies (Meyer-Krahmer and Schmoch, 1998; Acosta and Coronado, 2003). Consequently, current developments in science are important signals for identifying future’s promising technologies.

However, measuring and mapping of science-technology linkages has been proven challenging (Mansfield, 1991; McMillan et al., 2000; Narin et al., 1997). There are several data sources that are leveraged to identify direct science-technology linkages (Bekkers and Freitas, 2008), such as collaborations (Giunta et al., 2016) or the citation of non-patent-literature (NPL) in patents (Acosta and Coronado, 2003; Narin et al., 1997). However, such direct measures tend to be sparse and biased, since for instance joint university-industry patenting is the exception rather than the norm, and NPL citations are rarely used. Without such direct traces, author-matching and natural language processing (NLP) techniques have been used to identify paper-patent pairs (e.g., Magerman et al., 2015) which both relate to the same invention. Again, due

to division of labor and corporate IP strategies it is not uncommon that publication authors are not the same as the named inventors on a related patents, leading to similarly sparse results. Alternative indirect approaches to identifying science-technology linkages and to map technology applications arising from a particular field of scientific research focus on the identification of technologies within scientific literature, and in a separate step map them to technologically similar patents.

In this paper, we present a deep learning (DL) based approach to extract technology-related topics within scientific literature, and identify these technologies within patent applications. In detail, we utilize named entity recognition (NER) techniques and transformer-based text embeddings which are specifically fine-tuned to scientific literature to extract technology keywords. In a next step we cluster these keywords into human interpretable topics describing a certain technology application by a set of keywords related to the method as well as application and issues addressed. Finally, we create a large amount of search queries based on combinations of methods and applications, which we use in a semantic search to identify related patents.

We illustrate the workflow as well as results obtained by mapping publications within the field of neuroscience to related patent applications. This represents an interesting field to demonstrate the advantages of our approach, since neuroscience research has traditionally been an interdisciplinary research field where scientists from different disciplines like medicine, psychiatry, psychology, biology, biochemistry and linguistics work together (Schwechheimer and Winterhager, 2001). Throughout the last decade, technological change as well as changing global needs have lead to scientific as well as technological paradigm shifts in neuroscience and leading to development of the notion of neurotechnology. Research strands such as brain imaging, brain connectivity (Yeung et al., 2017), and lately neural computing (Savage, 2019) and neurodevices such as Brain Computer Interfaces (BCIs) have added to the diversity of technologies and potential applications. This degree of interdisciplinarity and dynamism limits the usefulness of traditional approaches to technology mapping via existing patent classifications. This has resulted in a limited overview over the types of technology applications in neuroscience, their scale, impact, and geography. Recently, academia and policymakers alike have recognised potential ethical and legal concerns related to the potentials of the latest generation of neurotechnology (Allhoff et al., 2011; Anderson et al., 2012; Drew, 2019; Dubljević et al., 2017; Jarchum, 2019), stipulated the formulation of guiding principles and regulations for future development (Gardenet et al., 2019). However, the formulation as well as the practical implementation of such principles requires a common understanding of what neuroscience is and is made of, in terms of both scientific and technological developments (neurotechnology), as well as possible applications.

By doing so, we aim at contributing to the growing body of research on text-based technology mapping and forecasting that leverages latest advanced in NLP and DL (Hain et al., 2022b,a, e.g., cf.). More specifically, we provide an approach that identifies technology related topics in scientific literature, and allows to disentangle keywords to identify methods and techniques embodied in the technology from the context and issue it is applied to. In contrast to Subject-Action-Object (SAO) (e.g., Yang et al., 2017) or ontology-based (e.g., Soo et al., 2006) approaches which are labor intensive, our work-flow allows to do so almost fully automated and is thereby highly scalable. We are able to map these technologies identified in scientific literature to patent applications, thereby providing an empirical foundation for the study of indirect science-technology linkages (e.g., Mansfield, 1991; Bekkers and Freitas, 2008; Acosta and Coronado, 2003). In contrast to existing approaches, neither a direct explicit link between publications and patents such as a NLP citation, nor the use of an exactly matching keyword terminology is necessary to identify applications of certain technologies. Our approach uses latest developments within transfer learning (Luan et al., 2018; Cohan et al., 2020; Grootendorst, 2020) in NLP to replicate, automate and scale the process of technology search as it is performed by a domain expert that, for instance, searches the patent landscape for related technologies during a novelty screening. The expert would typically derive relevant keywords from the description of a potential invention in part from the present text and in part relying on his or her expertise. While appropriate for individual inventions, such traditional and manual approaches are costly, time-consuming, and thus impractical for exercises at the present scale (Park and Yoon, 2017). Having identified related technologies we provide an inclusive and interdisciplinary mapping of patent applications related to neuroscience technology, we are able to inform the current discussion on the potential needs for regulatory framework targeting these technologies. The results of this mapping can be accessed and explored via an interactive application at <https://neuroscience-sci-pat.herokuapp.com/>.

Methods

The core challenge in this study is the identification of neuroscience patents, a broad and emerging field embracing multiple technologies from various disciplines. While we were able to use the broad subject area classification within *Scopus* for the identification of neuroscience research, there are no explicit categories for such interdisciplinary fields for patented technologies. The diversity of technologies and applications as well as rapid technological development prevents a inclusive identification via static technology classifications such as IPC or CPC.

In this paper we rely on a multi-step approach where we start with automated identification of latent themes (or topics) and keywords in the research literature. For each of these themes we use detected keywords and key-phrases to construct search queries that are subsequently used for semantic search within the patent database. This approach, illustrated in Figure 1, allows us to combine a broad scope of the overall search – neuroscience - with being able to restrict results to very specific

subfields such as for instance “Sleep and Memory Consolidation”. The approach can be combined with domain expertise, where after the detection of topics a domain expert would select those that are deemed relevant as foundation for technology identification. We report overall results for patents matched to all topics as well as selected topics that –without profound domain expertise – can be attributed to neurotechnology.

Figure 1: Macro overview of the analysis pipeline

Transformer based Topic Modelling

For the identification of latent themes within research literature, which in its outcomes is similar to traditional topic modelling, we build on top of BERTopic (Groendorst, 2020). There are various reasons why we chose this approach rather than traditional topic modelling techniques such as LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation, Blei et al. (2003)) or even simpler algorithms e.g. LSA (Latent Semantic Analysis, Deerwester et al. (1990)). First, we do not have actively preprocess text data, making it easier to transfer this work to other domains and facilitate use by others. While established algorithms are well suited to efficiently handle the size and type of data that we are working with, they require extensive preprocessing of text data before it is passed on. This would typically include, tokenization, removal of stopwords (e.g. and, the, pronouns etc.), taking decisions about potential removal of certain parts of speech (e.g. verbs, prepositions) as well as identification of bi- and n-grams that typically dominate scientific language. Modern transformer language models encapsulate these steps following well documented and benchmarked best practice, thus requiring less expertise within NLP for robust application.

Traditional statistical topic models are typically trained on and applied to the same

corpus. That means that they can not “learn” beyond the provided data. In contrast, modern transformer language models are pre-trained on vast amounts of text data and constantly evaluated following transparent protocols. The transfer learning approach, where models trained once on a large amount of data are then fine-tuned and applied to other, smaller data-sets has revolutionised the field of Natural Language Processing particularly since 2018 and the introduction of neural language models like BERT (Devlin et al., 2018). Text representations (embeddings) created using these models are contextualized, capture semantic and syntactic features, handle typical language processing problems such as synonyms and polysemy and have outperformed other approaches in many NLP tasks. Lastly, we use the hierarchical clustering technique HDBSCAN (McInnes et al., 2017) for the detection of topics. This allows us to set parameters that directly influence the specificity of identified topics in the literature. Rather than deciding about a fixed amount of topics upfront, we can set a threshold for the minimum number of documents that are allowed to form a topic. Thereby, we can minimize the number of parameters provided by the analyst, making the approach data-driven and easy to replicate/adopt to other domains as possible.

Our approach differs in 2 major points from BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2020): We use SPECTER a specialised model for scientific language rather than generic transformer models. We also use NER for the identification of keywords and key-phrases rather than simpler statistical strategies. Figure 2 depicts the different steps of this process. First, we embed the extracted abstracts using SPECTER (Cohan et al., 2020), a state of the art transformer language model for document-level embedding for scientific text. SPECTER has been developed as a tailor-made embedding model for scientific text and achieved state-of-the-art performance in the majority of document level tasks within the SciDOCS evaluation suite. The model is developed departing from SciBERT (Beltagy et al., 2019), which in turn has been pre-trained on 1.14M academic papers (full text). While SciBERT is a general language model, developed for NLP tasks within the near textual context (e.g., NER, classification), SPECTER incorporates citation information into the training process to capture signals of inter-document relatedness. This results in text representations that are well suited for “feature-based” downstream tasks, such as clustering or measuring of document similarity (Cohan et al., 2020) utilising other (non-neural) machine learning techniques.

We then use a combination of UMAP (Becht et al., 2019) and HDBSCAN (McInnes et al., 2017) to cluster documents. This combination of dimensionality reduction and density based clustering has shown to scale well while delivering efficient and stable performance, and being able to identify coherent groupings of documents. Discounting for unclustered records and those put into a “catch-all-cluster” we end up with 31957 documents distributed across 218 clusters or topics, with an average size of 148 and a maximum of 863. The minimum size has been set to be 50 as a hyper parameter during the clustering process.

Figure 2: Extended topic modeling pipeline

Named Entity Extraction for Science-keyword extraction

To create insightful cluster/topic-descriptors we use keywords and key-phrases generated using Named Entity Recognition (NER). Here we utilize a SciBERT transformer model, which we fine-tune to perform NER. We use the SciERC dataset (Luan et al., 2018) for the retraining. The dataset consists of 500 abstracts, mainly in the area of computer science, that have been manually annotated to mark *methods*, *tasks* and *other scientific keywords*. As mentioned above SciBERT is similarly to SPECTER a large transformer model developed to handle scientific text. Such language models can be retrained to perform specific language tasks such as question answering, summarization or as in our example NER. An advantage of such models is that a limited amount of training data (here, 500 annotated scientific abstracts) are sufficient to achieve good performance. The algorithm identifies and extracts “scientific keywords” sorted into the categories *task*, *method* and *other scientific terminology*

from the abstracts. Despite domain-transfer (from mainly computer science to interdisciplinary neuroscience) the retrained model is able to identify relevant keywords and phrases that can be used to describe detected topics. We argue that this constitutes a significant improvement over simple frequency-based methods for keyword extraction such as word/n-gram frequencies or algorithms like RAKE (Rose et al., 2010) that are commonly seen in combination with topic modelling exercises. Finally we weight these keywords by importance for the respective cluster/topic with simple TF-IDF (term frequency - inverse document frequency). A collection of keywords and key-phrases that represents an identified topic - using the above mentioned example - would typically look like: 'sleep', 'REM sleep', 'memory consolidation', 'spindles', 'sleep spindles', 'SWS', 'slow waves', 'slow-wave sleep', 'slow oscillation'. Here it is important to note, that phrases such as "slow-wave sleep" have been identified automatically, i.e. without the need to specify n-gram length or other parameters.

Figure 3: Topics over time (columns) 2000-2021 - screenshot of interactive chart, first 24 topics out of 218

Given that publications have a time dimension (publication date), we can map the development of topics over time and in relation to each other, which is visualized in Figure 3. Document embeddings are very flexible representations of text. For instance, we can further aggregate these fine-grained topics on higher levels, again using hierarchical clustering on the average-vectors calculated from the individual document vectors belonging to a topic. Figure 5 illustrates how these inter-topic dependencies can be presented in a dendrogram.

Figure 5: Cropped dendrogram, showing the relationship of individual topics

Conclusion

In this paper, we presented an efficient deep learning based approach to extract technology-related topics and keywords within scientific literature, and identify corresponding technologies within patent applications. We illustrated the workflow as well as results obtained by mapping publications within the field of neuroscience to related patent applications, aiming at the mapping of neurotechnology, and particularly the identification of emerging ones.

Specifically, we utilize transformer based language models, tailored for use with scientific text, to detect coherent topics over time and describe these by relevant keywords that are automatically extracted from a large text corpus. We identify these keywords using Named Entity Recognition, distinguishing between those describing methods, applications and other scientific terminology. These topics are created via density-based clustering of transformer based embeddings, which are fine-tuned to scientific literature. In contrast to traditional topic modelling techniques, our approach produces topics focused on the description of technologies and their applications rather than general themes in the corpus. We create a large amount of search queries based on combinations of method- and application-keywords, which we use to conduct semantic search and identify related patents. By doing so, we aim at contributing to the growing body of research on text-based technology mapping and forecasting that leverages latest advances in natural language processing and deep learning. We demonstrate at the case of neuroscience research, that the developed approach is able to extract technology topics in broad, interdisciplinary, and dynamic field, and map these topics to patent data. Enabling the semi-automatized mapping of technologies identified in scientific literature to patent applications, we are thereby providing an empirical foundation for the study of science- technology linkages.

The presented method as well as the obtained preliminary results are at its current stage subject to a number of limitations. As discussed in section 3, our main aim is to detect technology topics in scientific publications, use them to identify science-technology linkages, and finally map the development of neurotechnologies in patent data. To do so we create a neuroscience related corpus of scientific literature by

filtering Scopus by subject area. Subject areas are assigned on journal level, and rather broad, in this case ranging from computer science, over chemistry, biology, and psychology. While this is an inherent feature of neuroscience research, it complicates the identification of technology topics from the publications text data. While our approach is geared towards selecting terms related to scientific methods, many of them cannot be related to an actual technology, but rather a method of scientific inquiry within academia. A more focused and technology-targeted selection of publications could limit this effect. However, within the presented approach, the manual selection of relevant technology topics by a domain expert remains necessary. Furthermore, the presented approach assumes technologies to initially emerge in scientific literature, and then later being further developed to commercial technologies. Yet, it is reasonable that distinct technologies are emerging without former traces in science, or in commercial applications develop far away from their scientific origin in terms of methods and techniques as well as issues addressed. This could to some extent be addressed by extending the approach presented in this paper with additional iterative steps to identify additional technology topics within the selected patents, and expanding this selection to similar patents outside the current selection.

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